

Vibrational Spectroscopic investigation, Magnetic susceptibility, MEP, NBO, NLO, Fukui function and quantum chemical parameters analyses of 1(3, 4-Dichlorophenyl)ethanone

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Abstract

The molecular structure, vibrational spectra, NLO, NBO, MEP and HOMO, LUMO analysis of 1(3, 4-Dichlorophenyl)ethanone were reported. The vibrational wavenumbers were computed using DFT quantum chemical calculation. The data obtained from wavenumber calculations are used to assign vibrational bands obtained experimentally. HOMO and LUMO energies show that the charge transfers occur within the molecule. The Stability of the molecule arising from hyperconjugative interaction and charge delocalization has been analyzed using NBO analysis. Gauge-including atomic orbital ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectral assessment have been made choosing structure-property relationship by chemical shifts along with the magnetic shielding effects regarding the title compound. The first hyperpolarizability of the title compound is greater than that of the standard nonlinear optical (NLO) material urea and its derivatives are good objects for further research in nonlinear optical analysis. Magnetic susceptibility and thermodynamic properties have been determined for various ranges of temperature. Mulliken's net charges and the atomic natural charges have been calculated. Molecule sites prone to electrophilic and nucleophilic attacks have been detected by the calculation of average local ionization energies, while calculations of Fukui functions have provided additional information about the local reactivity properties.